

Capacity Building and State-Owned Universities Sustainability in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

State-owned universities in Nigeria face problems, including inadequate funding, budget deficit, weak revenue diversification and lack of sustainable financing mechanism. These problems tend erode university sustainability in the forms of non-payment of staff salaries, non-payment of promotion arrears when required among others. This study examined capacity building and state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria. Five research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was used and 616 teaching staff of the 3 oldest state-owned universities constituted the sample size. Multi-stage sampling technique, consisting of purposive and proportionate sampling techniques, were adopted. Self-developed questionnaire was used for data collection titled: Capacity Building Questionnaire (CBQ) with 0.90 as reliability coefficients. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysing research questions and testing hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that budget deficit, weak revenue diversification, inadequate revenue, inadequate funding by the government, weak internally-generated revenue (IGR), lack of a sustainable financing mechanism and inadequate university knowledge sharing with industry were among the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria. There was significant relationship between the explanatory variables (lecturers conferences, mentoring, seminar, workshop and ICT training) and the dependent variable (universities sustainability) in the order of magnitude thus: seminar ($r = 0.737$, $P < .05$), mentoring ($r = 0.735$, $P < .05$), conferences ($r = 0.500$, $P < .05$), workshop ($r = 0.211$, $P < .05$) and ICT training ($r = 0.129$, $P < .05$). The study recommended that, to increase their revenue-base, state government-owned universities must re-invent themselves as entrepreneurial and boundary spanning hubs working assiduously with industry players. University management should allocate more funds for teaching staff capacity building programme to update their intellectual knowledge.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Mentoring, Teaching-Staff, University Sustainability

Introduction

University sustainability is the capacity of universities to conduct research to find solutions to contemporary industrial and societal problems as well as generate revenue. It refers to maintaining the system's financial stability without sacrificing other required responsibilities. University sustainability is a potential solution to insufficient funding which is a fundamental issue undermining the effectiveness of education in Nigeria's public universities. State-owned universities are seeking to achieve sustainability; however, they have to adopt innovative strategies to achieve the quest. University sustainability entails the acquisition of sustainable financial resources for the system and reduction in over-reliance on government subvention. Sustainable

financial resources refer to the financial capacity of university to completely perform its financial obligations without full reliance on government subvention or loans.

University sustainability is the capability to meet legitimate and statutory needs of an entity or daily financial obligation of an organisation without external supports for finance or reliance on external influence for survival (Odewole, Olowookere and Oladejo, 2021). University sustainability deals essentially with two fronts: expanding the financial frontiers of the entities or widening the organisational resource baseline of an enterprise into a triple bottom line to gain a competitive financial edge (Odewole *et. al.*, 2021). University sustainability stretches to pull all weights into generating enough internal revenue within its limits of operations, opening up its revenue resource, and widening its circle of core competence to meet up all its expenses without third-party assistance for financial aids (Hahn and Figge, 2022). University sustainability is a key component used to assess the financial status of a university (Nalwoga, 2021). University sustainability is one of the most-important characteristics for evaluation of the financial situation of a university. Common criteria that determine the sustainability of a university are operational sustainability, liquidity and solvency (Sami and Sree, 2022). Sazonov, Kharlamova, Chekhovskaya and Polyanskaya (2020) measured university sustainability using dimensions of net operating results, income diversification, liquidity, and solvency or leverage while Ahmet and Premaj (2022) measured university sustainability through the capability of the university to generate revenue from creativity and novel innovations from the academic staff through their research outputs.

The attainment of universities sustainability is feasible when they begin to increase access to financial resources through sustained revenue and this has necessitated these institutions globally to undertake revenue enhancement measures and cost management initiatives to close budgetary gaps (Ayam, 2021). Globally, most especially in Africa, public universities seem to be currently facing attacks from multiple angles. For instance, it has been noted that government underfunding, increased competition and the need to pursue university education are some of the factors affecting university sustainability (Ivonne, 2020). Nowadays, sustainability is one of the key challenges facing public universities in Africa and the sustainability of public universities is threatened by cutbacks in public funding and society's growing demand for improvements in the volume and quality of services provided (Carlo, Modugno, Agasisti and Catalano, 2023). The major factor undermining the efficacy of university education in Nigeria is underfunding precipitated by lackadaisical attitude of government towards university education (Ndubuisi-Okolo and Dibua, 2023). Public universities in Nigeria today are beginning to look inwards to raise their internally-generated revenue (IGR) towards the attainment of sustainability.

Sponsoring for training and retraining in categories of capacity building programmes to show academic staff new methodology and ways to use their intellectual knowledge towards finding solutions to the contemporary society and industrial challenges may act as one of the ways university can generate revenue for substantiality (Adebayo, *et. al.*, 2022). Akuegwu, Nwi-ue and Etudor-Eyo (2013) cited in Adebayo *et. al.*, (2022) defined capacity building as a process of skills acquisition, exposure to new knowledge and sustaining abilities to cope within new development. Capacity building entails the ability to realise more skills and knowledge; us, this can be termed at individual level. At institutional level, it relates to enhancing institutions to predetermine viable policies and procedure for management effectiveness. At societal level, it comprises the inspiration and acquisition of ideas from public interaction for action. On that note, university as an

organisation is saddled with the impartation of knowledge and this function is administered by the teaching staff. For teaching staff to effectively enhance value-adding through teaching and research development, they are obliged to sustain knowledge. As stated by Akani (2017), individuals came into the world without knowledge or innovative ideas, but as they grow through interaction with peer and society at large and, above all, through training, they begin to accumulate skills and concepts that can transform into products and services. Acquisition of skill, idea and knowledge are the bedrock of capacity building. Capacity building is the idea of developing human knowledge and skills tailored towards achieving a specified goal.

Capacity building exposes individuals to new ways of doing things, new knowledge, the way to turn ideas to finished products and the way to supply long-term solution to society challenges (Poelzer, 2017). Capacity building relates to the method of developing skills to realise novel ideas. Akuegwu, Nwi-ue and Etudor-Eyo (2013) cited in Adebayo *et. al.*, (2022) were of the opinion that capacity building is a crucial determinant in driving university sustainability and directly affects teaching staff's professional advancement. Workshops, seminars, conferences, ICT training and mentoring among others were among the indications of capacity building programmes which can drive human capital development among the teaching staff that may eventually enhance university sustainability. Workshop is an exercise of group of individuals who assemble to share knowledge and skills towards goal achievement or for solving a challenge. The aim of workshop is to open a new way of doing thing, and new innovative ideas and skills (Ollor, 2021). Workshop may be a training programme like academic conference. Akpan and Ita (2015) defined academic conference as an avenue or a planned event for lecturers to debate research outputs and share novel ideas while seminar is an academic instruction that mostly takes place at a tertiary institution for presentation of academic work, discussion and sharing of knowledge towards achieving a specified goal. Seminars seem to reinforce reading and writing culture among lecturers. It also provides a viable avenue for researchers, students and lecturers to share knowledge, research outputs and discussion on the ways to supply solution to existing societal problems (Al'Adawi, 2017). For lecturers or teaching staff to be effective in delivery of their academic work in this new age of information and communication technology (ICT), ICT training becomes necessary for lecturers (Akpan, 2014). ICT training refers to line of data and communication training to expose lecturers to skills and competencies within the usage of ICT tools for instructional delivery, development of research outputs, processing as well as analysing and prediction of relationship or influence of variables. Acquisition and development of latest knowledge among lecturers could also happen within the department, above all from senior to junior lecturers' interaction which could take the shape of mentoring. Mentoring encompasses the flow of ideas, instructions, information and exchange of data from lecturers to lecturers. Emenyonu, Lasbrey and Ekwebelem (2020) define mentorship as a process of assisting a lecturer/teacher to accumulate full knowledge to perform effectively at work.

University sustainability is a challenge to the authority and other stakeholders in educational sector; however, previous observations have shown that there are many contending issues to be examined. Studies like Adelowo *et. al.*, (2019), Aldaz *et. al.*, (2020), Solís-Espallargas *et. al.*, (2019), Grecu and Ipina (2015), Amoda *et. al.*, (2020) and Akanni (2017) among others have examined related issues with regard to university sustainability. Their studies have not really captured how or the extent to which capacity building could help in achieving universities sustainability among state owned-universities in South-West, Nigeria; hence, the necessity for this study.

Statement of the Problem

State government-owned universities in Nigeria are facing series of financial challenges including budget deficit, weak revenue diversification, inadequate revenue, inadequate funding by the government, poor Internal Generated Revenue (IGR) among others. These problems have manifested in various ways; staff are being owed salaries, promotion arrears are not being paid as at when due, drastically reduction in running cost of each department, stationaries for each unit of the universities are not adequately supplied and many others. However, it is said that no organization can attain sustainability without adequate revenue to effectively operate the system. The problem of inadequate funding has therefore reduced the quality of university education in the area of research, provision of infrastructural facilities, teaching activities in the universities. Hence, the products of the institutions seem not to be adequately prepared and equipped for national development. Critical among these challenges is the lack of a sustainable financing mechanism which poses a threat to the development of quality university education in the country. It is also on notice that state-owned universities have experienced series of incessant strike actions by the staff and these actions seem to be affecting the standard of university education and their sustainability in the country. Majority of these incessant strike actions are associated with the problems of budget deficit as a result of inadequate funding of the university system. Governments have taken steps towards addressing these challenges through the establishment of Tertiary Education Trust (TETFund), increment in students' school fees (tuitions), and introduction of several fees among others. Despite that, university sustainability could not still be achieved in most of state government-owned universities in Nigeria. This study examined capacity building as ways towards the attainment of university sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine capacity building and state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

1. Identified the factors eroding state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.
2. Ascertained the relationship between capacity building and state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.
3. Determined the influence of capacity building on state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What are the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?
2. Could there be a relationship between capacity building and state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of capacity building on state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational research design. A correlational research design investigates relationships between two variables (or more) without the researcher controlling or manipulating

any of them. It is a non-experimental type of quantitative research. The reasons for using this design are that it provides insights into complex real-world relationships, helping the researcher develop research questions/hypotheses and make predictions on the extent to which independent (exogenous) variables relate with dependent (endogenous) variable. This design has been adopted by Ebisinkemefa and Lucky (2023) who examined the association between academic mentorship and lecturers' performance in tertiary educational institutions in Bayelsa State as well as Abubakar and Saka (2021) who examined the relationships among ICT training, skills acquisition, ICT use and job performance of librarians and library officers in universities in North-West, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 3,536 teaching staff of 9 state-owned universities who have been in operation for past 10 years in South-West, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in this study comprising three stages as follows:

Stage 1: State-owned universities that have been in operation for the past 10 years in South-West, Nigeria were first selected using purposive sampling technique. A stratum is a subset of the population that share at least one common characteristic.

Stage 2: Thereafter, three (3) (33.33%) oldest state-owned universities were selected also through purposive sampling technique. The selected universities are as follows:

Table 1: Selected oldest state-owned universities in South-West, Nigeria

S/N	Universities Name	States	Year of Establishments
1.	Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye (OOU)	Ogun	1982
2.	Ekiti State University (EKSU)	Ekiti	1982
3.	Lagos State University (LASU)	Lagos	1983

Source: Researcher, 2023

Stage 3: From this point, proportionate sampling technique of 38% was used in selecting 239 teaching staff from Lagos State University (LASU), 229 teaching staff from Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU) and 148 teaching staff from Ekiti State University making a total of 616 teaching staff as sample size of the study. A research instrument was adopted in this study titled: Capacity Building Questionnaire (CBQ). CBQ was a self-structured instrument geared towards eliciting information from lecturers' regarding their level of capacity building sponsored by the universities and university sustainability. The questionnaire requested responses on a four (4) – point scale format which was a modification of 5-point Likert scale. To ensure the face and content validity of the instruments, copies of instruments CBQ were made available to 5 experts from the Department of Business Education, Educational Management and Technology, Tai Solarin University of Education. Reliability of the instrument was done using the Cronbach Alpha. In this case, copies of the instrument CBQ were administered on 30 teaching staff of Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbami, Enugu, Nigeria parallel to the sample population. The collected data were analysed and reliability estimate was reported as 0.90. Primary and secondary methods of data collection were adopted in this study. A letter of introduction was collected from the Head of Department of Business Education, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State presented to the authorities of the selected state-owned universities in South-West, Nigeria for permission to include their teaching staff in the study. The consent of the teaching staff (respondents) were sought for participation in the study. The researcher, with the assistance of the trained research assistants, visited all the selected three (3) Universities in the

sampled states for data collection. The states visited were Ekiti, Lagos and Ogun The questionnaire, Capacity Building Questionnaire (CBQ) were administered in each of the sampled Universities on the sampled teaching staff. The exercise was completed within 6 months. As earlier stated, a total of 616 copies of questionnaires were administered and only 589 were retrieved. Retrieval/success rate was 95.6% and mortality rate 4.4%. Revenue generated through consultancy services were used as proxied for universities sustainability. These data were collected through secondary method of data collection and they are in numerical nature. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used as estimation techniques.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.

Factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability	Mean	SD
Budget deficit	3.18	.987
Weak revenue diversification	3.02	1.077
Inadequate revenue	3.38	.806
Inadequate funding by the government	3.19	.890
Weak internal generated revenue (IGR)	3.29	.961
Lack of a sustainable financing mechanism	3.32	.997
Inadequate university knowledge sharing with industry	2.68	1.209
Low level of university exploitation of ideas from research outputs	3.36	.799
Average Mean	3.18	

Source: Author Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 reveals average mean value of 3.18 and benchmark mean value of 2.50, indicating that $3.18 > 2.50$. This implies that budget deficit, weak revenue diversification, inadequate revenue, inadequate funding by the government, weak internal generated revenue (igr), lack of a sustainable financing mechanism, inadequate university knowledge sharing with industry and were among the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: Could there be a relationship between capacity building and state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 3: Correlation matrix of the independent and dependent variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	rc	rm	rs	rw	rict
Universities' sustainability	47.50	4.675	1.000				
Conferences	16.29	2.383	.500**	1.000			
Mentoring	15.66	2.338	.735**	.005	1.000		
Seminar	15.55	2.392	.737**	.013	.465**	1.000	
Workshop	16.69	2.194	.211**	.195**	.130**	.091*	1.000
ICT training	15.79	2.240	.129**	.075	.060	.268**	.211** 1.000

Source: Author Field Survey, 2024

Note: Where rc, rm, rs, rw and rict representing correlation coefficients for conferences, mentoring, seminar, workshop and ICT training (All are the indicators for capacity building for teaching staff). Table 3 reveals significant relationship between the independent variables (lecturers conferences, mentoring, seminar, workshop and ICT training) and the dependent variable (universities sustainability) in the order of magnitude seminar ($r = 0.737, P < .05$), mentoring ($r = 0.735, P < .05$), conferences ($r = 0.500, P < .05$), workshop ($r = 0.211, P < .05$) and ICT training ($r = 0.129, P < .05$). The implication of these results is that increase in sponsoring capacity building programmes for lecturers (teaching staff) could cause marginal increases in universities' sustainability in long run.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of capacity building on state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 4: Influence of capacity building on state-owned universities sustainability in South-West, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error				
1	(Constant)	30.907	2.927	10.561	.000	
	Capacity building	.495	.092	.217	5.396	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Universities' sustainability

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 shows that the sign of the coefficient of lecturers' capacity building was positive which implies that an increase or improvement in it will increase universities' sustainability. The independent variables were found to be significant and strongly determine universities' sustainability with the P-value less than 0.05 and magnitude of lecturers' capacity building ($\beta = 0.217, t = 5.396, P < .05$). The implication of this result is that a marginal increase in lecturers' capacity building would cause 21.7% increase in universities' sustainability.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that budget deficit, weak revenue diversification, inadequate revenue, inadequate funding by the government, weak internal generated revenue (igr), lack of a sustainable financing mechanism, inadequate university knowledge sharing with industry and were among the factors eroding state-owned universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria. These findings were in support to Ndubuisi-Okolo and Dibua (2023) who revealed that paucity of autonomy, poor management; political quagmire and insufficient funding are factors hampering financial sustainability of public universities while complete autonomy, federal/private funding, huge budget allocation, donor support and adopting foreign patterns of public universities' funding are valuable means of achieving financial sustainability of public universities in Nigeria. Afolayan and Bashorun (2022) who found that institutional challenges such as lack of training, lack of institutional support, lack of incentives and motivation, inadequate infrastructure, high rate of students' enrolment were among factors affecting universities' sustainability and engagement. Kalomo and Chama-Chiliba (2022) found that the institutional framework being used by UNZA for IIGAs was not sustainable and inadequate to cover or meet the current expenditure. The income or revenue generated from IIGAs was less than twice the amount spent by the university on expenditure. Moreover, staffing costs over the years under review could not be covered through UNZA's current internal income-generating activities.

Furthermore, the findings of the study correlate with Makoye (2022) who found that factors influencing the sustainability of HESLB includes fund from the government budget; efficient management of the scheme; cost efficiency; current ratio and effective loan payments. In addition, Makoye's (2022) findings revealed that government subvention, management efficiency, repayment rate and liquidity explain significant 55% variation of the HESLB sustainability. Ayam (2021) showed that governance framework, cost management and pricing approach were significant factors predicting a best fit equation for financial sustainability of universities. Chidi (2019) revealed that tertiary education in Nigeria is faced with several challenges and, therefore, the working conditions of academics leave much to be desired.

There was significant relationship between the independent variables (lecturers conferences, mentoring, seminar, workshop and ICT training) and the dependent variable (universities sustainability) in state government-owned universities in South-West, Nigeria. These findings were in support of Ibeme (2020) who revealed that direct mentoring had significant positive effect on the stock of research skills imparted to younger university lecturers and programmes facilitators by their senior colleagues; that indirect mentoring had no significant positive effect on the stock of pedagogical skills imparted to younger university lecturers and programme facilitators by their senior colleagues. Iwuchukwu and Echedom (2020) found that staff training and development programmes directly influence lecturers' human capital development for universities sustainability. Oguejiofor and Ezenwanne (2020) revealed that respondents strongly agreed that training and retraining programme may be a strategy for improving the standard of Business Education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. Nwamaka and Mbah (2019) showed that the capacity building for Building Construction lecturers in walling, roofing, columns and beams is required because the extent the lecturers performed the skill was less than the extent required for universities' performance and sustainability. Nwokedi *et. al.*, (2018) showed that

capacity building needs of Education lecturers in universities include knowledge of operating ICT devices, and good knowledge of handling the ICT devices in teaching for universities' performance and sustainability. Chukwuedo and Igbinedion (2014) revealed that TVE lecturers need capacity building within the use of ICT for instructional, research and administrative purposes.

Conclusion

The issues relating to state government-owned universities sustainability have become a source of concern to stakeholders in university education. Personal observations by the researcher revealed that lack of public universities' sustainability in Nigeria are among the reasons for perennial occurrence of ASUU strike; as records show that majority of these strikes are caused by inadequate funding of public universities by the government. State owned-universities have been found affected by inadequate funding by the government and this gap has prompted many of them to begin to look for alternative strategies to increase their revenue base. Based on this identified gap, this study examined how capacity building could be used for university sustainability. On that note, it was concluded that adequate sponsoring of conferences, mentoring, seminar, workshop, and ICT training for academic staff could enhance state government owned-universities' sustainability in South-West, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are provided for the study:

1. State government-owned universities must re-invent themselves as entrepreneurial and boundary-spanning hubs by working assiduously with industry players to increase their revenue-base.
2. State government-owned universities need to engage their alumni as partners, as universities in other climes do especially North America. Support from alumni is an area where many United States universities are leaving a lot of money on the table.
3. There should be government's adequate funding, tuition, research grants and donor support from alumni foundations, building strong partnership with private individuals and companies to attract funds for developmental purposes. This will help minimise the financial burden of state government-owned universities and make them financially stable to maintain internationally-acclaimed and respected global standards for sustainability.
4. Government, through university management, should allocate adequate funds to sponsor teaching staff capacity building programme to update their knowledge on how to develop their intellectual knowledge to compete with their counterparts in developed nations like United States of America, United Kingdom and China.
5. Senior lecturers should furnish mentoring programme for younger and less-experienced colleagues in form of conducting reputable research with solid contents for knowledge sharing with the industry. State government should continuously be given permission and sponsorship to lecturers to proceed on study-fellowship training programmes since their performance is enhanced through such trainings and retraining. There should be an open-door policy to all lecturers at state government owned-universities to allow all lecturers to attend conferences, seminars, workshops and ICT trainings every two years to better

demonstrate their professionalism, understanding of the ongoing need for professional learning and the broader role in research development for innovations development.

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